

Crystalline Components of the Roots of*Phyllanthus reticulatus*

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PHYLLANTHUS reticulatus Poir syn: *Kirganelia reticulatus* (Euphorbiaceae) is a bushy shrub growing in arid zones of India. A large number of *Phyllanthus* species have been examined¹⁻⁴ and found to contain alkaloids and lignans. The 50% ethanolic extract of *P. reticulatus* was screened for its various pharmacological activities in C.D R.I., Lucknow, in mice through intraperitoneal (i.p.) injection giving LD₅₀ 750 mg/kg. The gross effects observed at various doses were increased in spontaneous motor activity and respiration. The cardiovascular studies carried out in cat at 50 mg/kg (i.p.) dose showed 40% potentiation to histamine and fall in blood pressure was 10 to 30 mm of Hg.

Experimental*Methods and Apparatus :*

All melting points reported are uncorrected.

Thin-layer chromatograms were conducted on Merck's Kiesel gel G and the spray reagent used was 2% ceric sulphate in 2N H₂SO₄.

UV, IR, PMR and Mass spectra were recorded as usual.

Results and Discussion

Roots of Phyllanthus reticulatus: Completely dried and coarsely powdered roots were exhaustively extracted thrice with hot benzene for 24 hrs. The extract was chromatographed over deactivated Brockmann alumina (5% aqueous acetic acid) using solvents of increasing polarity yielding the following compounds.

Octacosanol: From pure light petrol, white crystalline solid, m.p. 82° was obtained; M⁺ 410, it appeared to be octacosanol by mixed m.p. and by preparation of its acetate (Ac₂O/Pyr.), m.p. 64°.

Taraxeryl acetate: From pure light petrol, colourless crystalline solid, m.p. 290° (C₈H₆), M⁺ 468, gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test. IR, ν_{max} KBr: 1725 (COCH₃), 1460, 1245, 975, 865 cm⁻¹, etc. Saponification with alcoholic 5% KOH gave an aglycone, m.p. 283°, M⁺ 426; IR, ν_{max} KBr: 3610 (O-H) cm⁻¹, identified as taraxerol. It was identified as taraxeryl acetate⁵ (m.m.p., TLC & IR) with an authentic sample.

Friedelin: Elution with pure petrol furnished white needles, m.p. 258-60° (petrol), M⁺ 426, IR, ν_{max} KBr: 1720 cm⁻¹ (C=O). From the above data it appeared to be friedelin⁶ and was further confirmed by its superimposable IR spectra with an authentic sample and Co-TLC.

Epifriedelinol: Elution with petrol-benzene (3:1) yielded shining flakes, m.p. 274-6° (C₈H₆), it gave positive colour tests for triterpenes. IR, ν_{max} KBr: 3600 cm⁻¹ (O-H), acetate, m.p. 290-2° and confirmed as epifriedelinol by comparison with an authentic sample.

Taraxerone: Elution with petrol-benzene (2:1) afforded white crystalline compound, m.p. 236-38° (CHCl₃-MeOH). LiAlH₄ reduction of the compound gave an alcohol, taraxerol, m.p. 278-80°, its acetate taraxeryl acetate, m.p. 288-90°. It was identified as taraxerone⁷.

Betulin: Elution with petrol-benzene (1:1) gave white crystals, m.p. 249-51° (EtOAc); C₃₀H₅₀O₂, IR, ν_{max} KBr: 3390 cm⁻¹ (O-H), acetate, m.p. 214-5°, identical with an authentic sample of betulin.

β-Sitosterol: Elution with petrol-benzene (1:1) yielded colourless flakes, m.p. 136-7° (MeOH), acetate, m.p. 124-5° and identified as β-sitosterol.

Glochidonol: Elution with pure benzene furnished an amorphous powder, m.p. 228-30° (C₆H₆), IR, ν_{max} KBr: 3430 (O-H), 1725 (C=O), 3080, 1650 and 880 cm⁻¹, etc., acetate, m.p. 194-5° (CH₃OH), the above evidences confirmed that the compound is glochidonol⁸.

21α-Hydroxyfriedelan-3-one: Elution with benzene gave white crystalline compound, m.p. 263-66° (CHCl₃-MeOH), M⁺ 442, its analysis agreed to its molecular formula C₃₀H₅₀O₂, IR, ν_{max} KBr: 3510 (O-H), 1710 (C=O) cm⁻¹, etc. It was finally confirmed by mixed m.p. determination and superimposable IR and Co-TLC as 21α-hydroxyfriedelan-3-one⁹.

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Aurantiamide Acetate from *Artocarpus integrefolia* Linn.

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IN course of our investigation on some Indian medicinal plants, we were interested to examine the seeds of *Artocarpus integrefolia* Linn. which has been found to elaborate a number of flavones, steroids and triterpenes. Here we report the isolation of a dipeptide which has been identified as Aurantiamide acetate(I), the first known dipeptide of the plant origin, previously isolated from the seeds of *Piper aurantiacum* Wall¹.

The petroleum-ether extract of the dried seeds of *Artocarpus integrefolia* Linn. (pretreated with acetone in cold) furnished colourless silky needles on keeping in cold. The compound $C_{27}H_{28}N_2O_4$, M^+ 444, m.p. 188-89°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 30.65$ ($CHCl_3$) was neutral in character (yield 0.0004%).

The IR spectrum showed the characteristic band for acetoxy function at ν_{max} (KBr) 1720, 1249 and 1042 cm^{-1} , NH function at 3330 cm^{-1} , amido carbonyl at 1652 cm^{-1} , aromatic system at 1620, 1515 and 1484 cm^{-1} and mono-substituted phenyl nucleus at 740 and 690 cm^{-1} .

The UV absorption spectrum showed λ_{max} 213 and 230 nm with log ϵ values 3.37 and 3.19 respectively, suggesting the presence of aromatic system in the compound.

The PMR spectrum (90 MHz, $CdCl_2$, TMS) showed the presence of aromatic, amido, benzylic, methine and acetate protons in it. The δ -values are

7.53-7.90 (m, 5H, a), 7.4 (sh. s, 5H, b), 7.21 (br. s, 5H, b'), 6.9 (br. d, J=9.0 Hz, 1H, c), 6.2 (br. d, J=8.5 Hz, 1H, c'), 4.86 (m, 1H, d), 4.26-4.41 (m, 1H, d'), 3.95 & 3.83 (dd, J=6 & 3Hz, 2H, e' & e''), 3.20 & 3.10 (dd, J=8.5 & 9.5 Hz, 2H, e''' & e'''), 2.73 (d, J=7Hz, 2H, f), 1.98 (s, 3H, g).

The Mass Spectrum of the compound showed the loss of 60, 77, 91, 105 etc. units supporting the presence of acetoxy, phenyl, benzyl and benzoyl groups respectively. Other significant peaks also are in consistent with the structure(I).

The physical data are suggestive that it is a dipeptide identical to Aurantiamide acetate. This is the second-time isolation of the dipeptide from plant origin. The direct comparison with authentic specimen was not possible for paucity of material of the previous workers.

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Chemical Examination of Essential Oil of *Coleus aromaticus* Benth

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PLANT : *Coleus aromaticus* Benth (Family-Labiatae)
Isolation Procedure : Steam Distillation (Yield-0.04-0.05%), *Physical Constants* : Sp. gravity 0.9254, n_D^{20} 1.4896, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 8^{\circ}36'$, Acid value 3.276, Ester value 6.1314, Ester value after acetylation 152.576 and carbonyl value as $C_{10}H_{16}O$ -2.58%.

Previous Work : Few workers^{1,2} have reported the chemistry of essential oil obtained from leaves and separated phenolic and non-phenolic terpenes of the oil.

The completely characterised constituents of the oil are listed in Table 1.